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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20082615>**Abstract**

The influence of wind force on pollution of the urban atmosphere is considered. The bulk of suspended matter in the summer atmosphere of Yakutsk consists of fine sand and large dust particles, and in the winter - of small dust particles. Due to the geological and landscape features of the urban area and the spread of unimproved areas, with strong winds there is an increase in the concentration of dust in the air due to blowing sand. In the spring and summer months from April to July, with an average monthly wind force of 2.0-3.1 m/s, the concentration of dust in the air increases by 2-3 times. The maximum volume of Pb fallout from the atmosphere of 1.2 g/m² is observed in June and July with abnormal wind speeds of 2.3-3.1 m/s and dust content of 140-150 g/m³.

Keywords: pollution, urban, atmosphere, wind, lead**Introduction**

Unfavorable meteorological conditions lead to a sharp increase in concentrations of harmful substances in the ground layer of the atmosphere. It has now been established that there is a definite relationship between air pollution levels and climatic factors. The degree and intensity of air pollution are influenced by terrain, wind direction and speed, humidity, the amount, intensity, and duration of precipitation, air circulation, inversions, etc. [5] During certain periods unfavorable for emission dispersion, concentrations of harmful substances can increase sharply relative to average or background urban pollution. The frequency and duration of periods of high air pollution depend on the emission regime, as well as the nature and duration of meteorological conditions that contribute to increased concentrations of impurities in the ground layer. Wind can facilitate the dispersion of pollutants when they linger over a particular region. It can also carry pollutants far from their source. Within urban areas, low wind speeds can also be hazardous. Thus, at wind speeds of up to 1–2 m/s, toxic substances from ventilation systems settle near the ground, while at wind speeds of 4–6 m/s, toxic substances from large power plants settle near the ground. The resulting heat waves can lay the foundation for hazardous air quality conditions. According to research [4], air layers in inversion interact with heat and pollutants in urban areas, causing severe air pollution. The Yakutsk region is located in the Tuymada Valley, where air circulation is hampered by urban heat and poor ventilation to disperse pollutants beyond the city limits.

Research Results and Discussion.

Air pollutants (PM) are solid particles, atmospheric aerosols that directly enter the air, and particles formed during the transformation of gases. Particle sizes in the air range from 0.01 to 100 μm (PM_{0.01-100}). PM is an abbreviation for "particulate matter," and the number indicates the content of all particles

with a diameter of 0.01-100 μm. A serious threat to human health has been identified when exposed to them [4]. The level of PM pollution is one of the most important indicators of the quality of the air that people breathe. PM is undifferentiated dust (aerosol) contained in the air of populated areas; its harmfulness index is resorptive action, hazard class 3 [3]. Chemical elements of various toxicity classes present in PM, including Pb - toxicity class 1, can also pose a threat to public health [1]. A study of the amount of suspended matter (dust) and atmospheric precipitation was conducted at the Tuymada Complex Geocryological Station of the Institute of Earth Sciences SB RAS and in Yakutsk in 2024. Analytical processing of geochemical samples was conducted at the Laboratory of Groundwater and Cryolithozone Geochemistry of the Institute of Earth Sciences SB RAS (analysts L. Yu. Boytsova, E. S. Petrova, and O. V. Shepeleva) and at the Analytical Certification Testing Center of the Institute of Problems of Microelectronics Technology and High-Purity Materials of the Russian Academy of Sciences. The amount of atmospheric fallout (P) arriving with precipitation on the Earth's surface was calculated using the formula:

$$P = \frac{100 \cdot C \cdot V}{\pi \cdot r^2}, \text{ mg/m}^2,$$

where C is the concentration in the sample solution, mg/ml; V is the test volume, ml; r is the radius of the sample vessel neck, mm.

Suspended matter is undifferentiated dust (aerosol) contained in the air of populated areas; the hazard indicator is resorptive effect, hazard class 3, along with toxic metals such as V, W, Mn, Ge, etc. MAC value (mg/m³): maximum one-time – 0.5, average daily – 0.15. Almost two-thirds of the suspended matter mass in the summer urban atmosphere consists of fine sand and large dust particles with a diameter of 10-100 μm - PM₁₀₋₁₀₀ (Table 1). Suspended matter in the winter atmosphere consists of fine dust and clay particles with a diameter of less than 10 μm (PM_{≤10}).

Table 1

Grain size distribution of explosives in the atmosphere of Yakutsk [2]			
Particle fractions	Particle diameter, mm	Occurrence, %	
		Summer	Winter
Coarse and coarse sand	2000-500	1,2	-
Medium sand	500-250	4,0	-
Fine sand	250-100	17,0	-
Very fine sand	100-50	30,0	-
Coarse dust	50-10	38,0	-
Fine dust	10-2	9,0	80
Clay	<2	0,8	20
Dust amount, g/m ²			
Background, C _{geom}		1,09	0,77
Environmental assessment of the atmosphere in Yakutsk			
Dust concentration / Sanitary standard		2,1	1,6

Concentrations of dust (suspended solids, or PM) in the city's air consistently exceed the MACs. Average annual PM concentrations are 1.8 times higher than sanitary standards: 2.1 times higher in summer and 1.6 times higher in winter. Rain can help dilute high concentrations of pollutants in the air. Because coarse particulate matter (PM10), such as dust, dirt, and pollen,

are larger and heavier than other particles, rain can help PM10 settle to the ground more quickly, but is less effective at diluting smaller PM2.5 particles. However, rainfall in Yakutsk is short-lived and occurs during periods of peak winds. Table 2 shows precipitation data, including precipitation amount, dust content, and wind strength at the site.

Table 2

	.2024 year												C _{average}
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	
Wind, m/sec	0,7	0,9	1,7	2,3	3,0	3,1	2,3	2,0	3,1	1,9	1,0	1,1	1,9
Precipitation, mm	7,0	18,2	9,9	7,0	7,0	45,5	47,1	35,4	20,1	25,3	15,1	8,3	20,5
Dust, mg/L	33,6	50,0	64,5	105,3	105,3	151,9	136,8	142,9	37,0	47,1	40,0	34,5	80,0

For low-level and unorganized emission sources, elevated air pollution levels occur during light winds due to the accumulation of pollutants in the surface layer of the atmosphere, while during very strong winds, concentrations decrease due to rapid transport.

However, due to the geological and landscape features of urban areas and the prevalence of undeveloped areas, strong winds increase dust concentrations in the air due to the blowing of sandy material (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Relationship between wind speed and atmospheric dust concentration

In the spring and summer months from April to July, with average monthly wind speeds of 2.0-3.1 m/s, dust concentrations in the air rise to 100-150 mg/L.

Dust pollution levels increase two to three times compared to those at other wind

Figure 2. Atmospheric dust fallout in Yakutsk (summer)

1 – observation points; 2-5 – dust fallout, g/m² per day: 2 – ≤ 0.01 ; 3 – $0.01-1.0$; 4 – $1.0-5.0$; 5 – ≥ 5.0 .

Atmospheric dust fallout in summer and winter differs by an order of magnitude, 0.720 and 0.068 g/m², respectively. Urban dust contains elements of toxicity class III (Ba, V, W, Mn, Sr), class II (B, Co, Ni, Mo, Cu, Sb, Cr), and even class I (As, Cd, Hg, Pb, Zn) [5]. Let's consider the relationship between wind force and the concentration of one of the toxic metals, Pb, in atmospheric dust. During the summer months, throughout the warm period from May to August, at wind

speeds of 2-3 m/s, an increase in the volume of toxic metal deposition from the atmosphere is observed: twice the average in May and August (0.2-0.5 g/m²) and an order of magnitude increase to 0.5-1.2 g/m² in June and July at wind speeds of 2.3-3.1 m/s and dust concentrations of 140-150 g/m³ (Figure 3). The high input of Pb into the atmosphere and subsequent deposition on the earth's surface is determined by wind speed and the associated increase in air dustiness.

Figure 3. Relationship between wind force and Pb deposition with atmospheric dust

Conclusions.

Investigating the patterns of atmospheric pollutant propagation and the characteristics of their spatiotemporal distribution depending on the wind regime of an area provides the basis for an objective assessment of the state and trends of air pollution, as well as the development of potential measures to ensure atmospheric cleanliness. The nature of pollutant transport and dispersion depends primarily not only on the wind regime and emission source, but also on the nature of the substrate. Air pollutants include smoke, soot, dust, and liquid droplets generated during economic activity (fuel combustion) and present in the air. Suspended particles can cause both chemical air pollution (due to high concentrations of toxic substances) and biological pollution due to the presence of harmful microorganisms, including bacteria, viruses, and fungi. The bulk of urban atmospheric dust (PM) is formed by the blowing of roadside soils, the use of de-icing sand, atmospheric aerosol deposition, and the impact of vehicles and infrastructure. Urban dust accumulates pollutants from various components of the urban landscape and, in turn, is a significant source of soil, aquatic landscapes (lakes), and air pollution, contributing approximately 70% of the PM₁₀₋₁₀₀ particle mass to the city's atmosphere. In the spring and summer months from April to July, with average monthly wind speeds of 2.0-3.1 m/s, urban air pollution increases two- to three-fold, with dust concentrations reaching 100-150 mg/L. In June and July, with wind speeds of 2.3-3.1 m/s and dust concentrations of 140-150 g/m³, urban air pollution increases two- to three-fold. Pb deposition volumes reach maximum values of 0.5-1.2 g/m². High atmospheric Pb emissions and subsequent deposition on the Earth's surface are determined by wind speed and the associated

increase in air dustiness. To prevent the negative impact of elevated air pollution on health, especially in June and July, it is necessary to forecast and take into account adverse meteorological conditions and warn residents about "bad" days.

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